

ASSESSMENT OF THE EFFICIENCY OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE COMPETITIVE STRATEGY OF LOGISTIC ACTIVITY MANAGEMENT OF AGRICULTURAL ENTERPRISES IN THE CONDITIONS OF THE ONLINE MARKET

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Abstract

An important condition for the implementation of an effective competitive strategy for managing the logistics activities of agrarian enterprises in the online market is the development of a methodology for its assessment. At this time in the scientific world, scientists have not finally formed the optimal method of such assessment. Therefore, the topic of our article is relevant and important in today's conditions. The development of methods for assessing an effective competitive strategy for the management of logistics activities of agrarian enterprises in the online market will ensure the development of optimal system for making and supporting logistics decisions, will allow managers to distinguish productive and unproductive operations or management actions. The aim of the article is to develop a methodology for assessing the competitive strategy for managing the logistics activities of agrarian enterprises in the online market, which will improve the logistics system of the enterprise, form an effective logistics chain and increase the profitability of production.

Basis of the study are agricultural enterprises of Ukraine and their annual financial statements (balance sheet and reports on financial results), as well as indicators

of current logistics activities. The methodology for assessing the competitive strategy for managing the logistics activities of agrarian enterprises in the online market is proposed to be developed using the mathematical modeling method, which involves the use of artificial neural networks and specialized software (MATLAB, which includes the Neural Network Toolbox application package). The use of artificial neural networks in our study solves the problems of: limited input information, when traditional mathematical models do not give the desired result; increase the accuracy of calculations and reduce their subjectivity; simultaneously combine different methods of analysis and a large number of algorithms; make management decisions quickly.

An artificial neural network has been developed to predict the competitiveness of the logistics activities of agricultural enterprises. Using the developed neural network, the forecast values of the level of competitiveness of agricultural enterprises are calculated. It was determined that the highest level of reliability of the logistics system was obtained by the company STOV "Victory" (2.02 units), and the lowest - PE "Nagy" (1.79 units). Based on these calculations,

scenarios for ensuring competitive advantages in the future are proposed for each of the enterprises.

An assessment of the competitive strategy for managing the logistics activities of agrarian enterprises in the online market will provide a positive result, which is reflected in a slowdown in the growth rate of operating costs. This assessment contributes to the optimal logistics decision to ensure the strategic development of the agricultural enterprise. The developed methodology will be useful for entrepreneurs who are trying to increase the profitability of their enterprise through efficient logistics activities in conditions of uncertainty and speed of change in the environment.

Key words: *Online market, Management, Agrarian enterprises, Logistics system, Neural network.*

1. Introduction

In order to form and implement an effective competitive strategy for the logistic activity of the agricultural enterprise, it is necessary to carry out individual management actions. For enterprises to make informed and adequate management decisions, it is advisable to have information about the future of the agricultural producers, which is possible in assessing the effectiveness of the implementation of a specific logistic management strategy. Many authors have investigated the effectiveness of logistic management. The article of Gružauskas *et al.*, [1], proposed the forecasting of logistic clusters activity in the food industry. The authors [2 - 4] used in their researches an innovative methodology that can be adapted to determine the specificity of the management strategy of agribusiness logistic activity in the online marketplace. Li *et al.*, [5], proposed a methodology and model for selecting suppliers in the logistic chain using fuzzy logic, which facilitates the promotion and distribution of entrepreneurs' goods in the market. Garcia-Rodriguez *et al.*, [6], Bosona and Gebresenbet, [7], Tang and Veelenturf, [8], has studied the management and evaluation of logistic activity in depth. Researchers Semenov *et al.*, [9], have noted the need for resource-saving by agribusinesses, which should also be considered in the management of the logistic activity. Yang *et al.*, [10], He and Shi, [11], Yue *et al.*, [12], have noted the need to use information technology and modern means of automated information processing in the process of management of logistic activity of modern enterprises. Mayovets *et al.*, [13], used simulation modelling to prevent bankruptcy in agribusinesses, which is appropriate to use in the process of managing the logistic activity of these enterprises. This is particularly important given that effective logistic activities prevent bankruptcy and increase the profitability of enterprises. Relevant

studies for our article are the works of Ilinova *et al.*, [14], Ibn-Mohammed *et al.*, [15]. Cui *et al.*, [16], Gonzalez *et al.*, [17], and Ali *et al.*, [18], which proves that Covid-19 had a significant impact on the concreteness of enterprises and changed the logistic relationships. The mentioned above brings up to date the problem of assessing the effectiveness of the implementation of concreteness strategy for the management of logistic activity of agribusinesses. Innovative measures of management of agricultural enterprises, which are appropriate to use in logistic activity are proposed in the works of Khodakivska *et al.*, [19], Mazur *et al.*, [20], and Rossokha *et al.*, [21]. The evaluation of logistic chain efficiency by innovative methods is defined in Latino *et al.*, [22], Xu and He [23], and Lu *et al.*, [24], which also propose directions for improving logistic connections. Zos-Kior *et al.*, [22], focuses attention on the problems of investment support of agribusinesses, which are also important to maintain effective logistic activity. Sergi *et al.*, [26], proposed rather an innovative approach to the assessment of logistic activity of enterprises in Africa, Asia and the EU regions using the ANOVA method. In the work of the authors Hnatenko *et al.*, [27], was noted a methodology for assessing the innovation potential of an enterprise, the mathematical model of which is appropriate to use to evaluate the logistic activity of agricultural enterprises. Kayvanfar *et al.*, [28], proposed an adaptive stochastic model for the supply chain of small and medium-sized enterprises cohesive in industrial clusters.

Noting the importance of the above-mentioned works of scientists for assessing the effectiveness of the implementation of a competitive strategy for managing the logistic activity of agribusinesses, we should identify the lack of such an assessment in the online marketplace. That's why the aim of the article is to develop a methodology for assessing the competitive strategy for managing the logistics activities of agrarian enterprises in the online market, which will improve the logistics system of the enterprise, form an effective logistics chain and increase the profitability of production.

2. Materials and Methods

A total lack of foresight can paralyse an entire business. We propose to choose scenario planning and artificial networks as tools to assess the effectiveness of the implementation of a competitive strategy for managing the logistic activity of agribusinesses in the online marketplace. The scenario method, due to the need to predict the elements of logistic systems, has the characteristic of being a method of multidimensional predictive evaluation. Artificial neural networks make it possible to achieve a new quality of work, to obtain an economic effect from their implementation, or to

organize the process of management decision-making in a new way. The MATLAB software system, which includes the Neural Network Toolbox application package, is an option. Artificial neural networks used are three-layer networks of interconnected neurons, each of which can be described by an equation:

$$y = \int (w_1x_1 + w_2x_2 + \dots + w_nx_n + b_0) = \int \left(\sum_{i=1}^n w_i x_i + b_0 \right) \quad (1)$$

Where: n is the number of input neurons; x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n is the value of the input variable; w_i is a weighting factor that determines the influence of the appropriate values on the neurons; b_0 is a constant, i.e. an offset; \int - some non-linear function, i.e. neuronal activation function; y is the initial values of the neurons.

For the input neurons layer, the input values are the reliability parameters of each of the spheres of logistic activity of the agricultural enterprise before the beginning of the period, e.g.:

- X_1 - coefficient of reliability of the logistic supply chain;
- X_2 - coefficient of reliability of the production logistic system;
- X_3 - coefficient of reliability of the logistic transport system;
- X_4 - coefficient of reliability of the sales logistic system;
- X_5 - coefficient of reliability of the warehousing logistic system; and
- X_6 - is an integral indicator of logistic performance.

For the output neurons layer, the output parameters are some of the reliability parameters of the logistic system by the end of the period. The output values of the output neurons layer form the same set of competitiveness of each of the spheres of logistic activity of agricultural enterprises, as in the input of the networks, only by the end of the period. Namely, y_r for the output layer of neurons will correspond to x_r of the input layer (y_1 - reliability coefficient of the logistic supply system, y_2 - reliability coefficient of the logistic production system, y_3 - reliability coefficient of the logistic transportation system, y_4 - reliability coefficient of the logistic sales system, y_5 - reliability coefficient of the logistic warehouse system, y_6 - an integral indicator of logistic efficiency). As the value of x_r , it is reasonable to choose the parameter of an enterprise that is available, i.e. the data of financial and economic reporting for several years, which allows tracking the dynamics of the competitiveness of enterprise logistic systems for a sufficiently long time; there usually several numbers of such parameters. When choosing the structure of an artificial neural network, it should be noted that of the well-known structures of neural networks for researching the competitiveness of logistic systems of enterprises, the following deserve attention: forward propagation neural networks with backpropagation of errors in the process of training the networks; recurrent neural network with feedback.

One of the most common neural networks of this type is the Hopfield network.

The more common of the first types of neural networks are the three-layer neural network with an input layer of neurons to which the input value is fed, an inner (hidden) layer and an output layer of neurons.

One of the variants of usage of neural networks of direct propagation for assessing the competitiveness of each of the areas of logistic activity of an agricultural enterprise should be considered. On the input of the neural networks is a set of values characterizing the most important indicators before the beginning of the reporting period: x_{ij} ; $i = \overline{1, m}$; $j = \overline{1, n}$, where i is an ordinal number of the year; j is an ordinal number of parameter. On the output of the neural networks we get the same set of values, but by the end of the year (initial for the planned year) - $x_{i+1,j}$. Economic and mathematical models of enterprises should transform x_{ij} into $x_{i+1,j}$ for several periods for which statistical data are known. This transformation is realised through neural network training procedures, in the process of which the relationship coefficient w_{kl} between neurons and the bias b_r , are determined so as to minimise the sum of squares of deviations from a given value at the output of the neural networks. This process is carried out from outputs to inputs and is referred to as backward error propagation. The actual parameters of the functioning of enterprise logistic systems can be both measurable and dimensionless, moreover, the range of their values can differ by several orders of magnitude. In this regard, the input data is prenormalised so that it is in the range (-300, 300) or (0; 300) corresponding to the output values of bipolar and unipolar types of neuron activation functions. After the training procedures (carried out by the chosen method of optimization - gradient method), the constructed models of competitiveness of logistic systems of agrarian enterprises can be used for versatile research, namely, to develop forecasts, including to determine the reliability coefficient of each sphere of logistic activity, to establish the most critical parameters serve to calculate the integral indicator of logistic activity efficiency. To do this, each of the input parameters is modified $\pm \Delta x_i$ and determine a corresponding change of all output parameters $\pm \Delta x_i$.

The construction of a neural network model and prediction of indicators that characterize the competitiveness of the main areas of logistic activity are considered on the example of agricultural enterprises. Based on the data from the annual financial statements of agricultural producers, namely balance sheets and financial results reports, the reliability coefficients of the logistic system of different areas of logistic activity are calculated. The structure of an artificial neural

network to simulate the strategic level of logistic performance of agricultural companies with a limited set of characteristics is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of a neural network for predicting the reliability indicators of an agricultural enterprise's logistic system in an online marketplace
Source: Built by the authors

The neural network consists of three layers of neurons: an input layer (6 neurons) to which input values x_1, \dots, x_6 , are fed, an internal layer (3 neurons) and an external layer (6 neurons) from which input values y_1, \dots, y_6 , are obtained. Preliminarily the input and output parameters are normalized so that their numerical value is in the range (0; 300). The next step after the construction of the neural network involves the procedure of its training, i.e. after the training procedures, the results of the neural network

calculation of the output parameter with a given input parameter are checked.

3. Results and Discussion

Using artificial neural networks, we obtain forecast values of the above indicators, which will be used in modelling development scenarios when forming strategies to ensure competitive advantages of agrarian enterprises (Table 1).

The data show that the reliability of the logistic systems of the enterprises under study will continue to show an upward trend over the forecast years. At the same time, the integral indicators will remain almost stable in the strategic period. The usage of artificial neural networks in modelling of scenarios of development in the implementation of strategies to ensure the competitive advantages of enterprises allows not only to predict the main indicators of logistic activity of agrarian enterprises for several future periods, but also to analyse how changes in each of them will affect the change in the integral evaluation of the competitiveness of the logistic system. The results of this analysis are the basis for modelling optimistic, realistic and pessimistic scenarios.

Graphical interpretation of the process of modelling scenarios of strategic development of logistic activity using artificial neural networks in the implementation of a competitive strategy for the management of

Table 1. Forecast values of indicators of competitiveness of spheres of logistic activity of agrarian enterprises in the conditions of the online market

Indicators	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026
PE "Nad"					
Coefficient of reliability of the logistic supply chain	154,1	155,3	157,9	156,4	159,2
Coefficient of reliability of the production logistic system	7,9	8,2	8,6	8,5	8,8
Coefficient of reliability of the logistic transport system	23,7	23,9	23,9	23,6	24,0
Coefficient of reliability of the sales logistic system	148,4	149,1	153,3	149,3	154,8
Coefficient of reliability of the warehousing logistic system	21,1	23,5	23,8	23,4	24,1
An integral indicator of logistic performance	1,77	1,78	1,79	1,78	1,79
ALLC "Victory"					
Coefficient of reliability of the logistic supply chain	196,4	198,2	197,9	198,0	200,7
Coefficient of reliability of the production logistic system	36,6	38,1	37,8	38,2	39,9
Coefficient of reliability of the logistic transport system	80,4	82,3	81,7	82,0	84,4
Coefficient of reliability of the sales logistic system	220,3	221,1	219,6	219,9	221,3
Coefficient of reliability of the warehousing logistic system	35,8	36,9	35,1	35,8	39,2
An integral indicator of logistic performance	2,00	2,01	2,01	2,01	2,02
LLC "Beevo"					
Coefficient of reliability of the logistic supply chain	266,5	268,2	269,4	272,1	273,3
Coefficient of reliability of the production logistic system	49,4	51,3	52,8	52,9	53,7
Coefficient of reliability of the logistic transport system	6,9	7,2	7,4	7,7	7,8
Coefficient of reliability of the sales logistic system	246,1	252,4	256,1	258,8	260,6
Coefficient of reliability of the warehousing logistic system	41,8	43,2	44,5	46,5	49,0
An integral indicator of logistic performance	1,91	1,92	1,92	1,93	1,93

Source: Calculated by the authors.

logistic activity of agricultural enterprises is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Schematic representation of the process of modelling scenarios in the implementation of competitive strategies for managing the logistic activities of agricultural enterprises in the online marketplace

Source: Built by the authors

The main methods for modelling scenarios are: pessimistic scenario - a forecast of the development of situations by extrapolating existing trends in the future or projecting a possible change; optimistic scenario

- a forecast of the development of situations with a certain set of management measures oriented towards the interest of the stakeholder; realistic scenario - a set of measures to achieve the desired configurations of the situation. The scenario approach contributes to making management decisions by reviewing the final result and choosing the most effective one. Given the significant influence of profit and costs of an agricultural enterprise on the formation of logistic systems reliability indicators, it is advisable to apply a scenario approach to determine exactly the amount of gross profit depending on the changes in net income and cost of goods sold (Table 2). The simulation of scenarios and the results of calculations are given in Table 3.

The analysis has been carried out with the help of the Excel Scenario Manager. Depending on the scenario, the gross profit of PE "Nad" varies from 6,545 to 21,516 thousand euros, of ALLC "Victory" - from 3,855 to 14,254 thousand euros, of "Beevo" Ltd. there are two negative scenarios with a probability of loss, as

Table 2. Projected values of net income amount and cost of sales for scenario development

Indicators	Realistic scenario	Pessimistic scenario	Optimistic scenario
	3 - 5% indicators improvement	Deterioration of indicators by 10%	10% indicators improvement
PE "Nad"			
Net income from sales of products, thousand euros	46219 (N1)	39997 (N2)	48885 (N3)
Cost of goods sold, thousand uros	29498 (C1)	33452 (C2)	27370 (C3)
ALLC "Victory"			
Net income from sales of products, thousand euros	31447 (N1)	27478 (N2)	33584 (N3)
Cost of goods sold, thousand euros	20833b(C1)	23624 (C2)	13448 (C3)
LLC "Beevo"			
Net income from sales of products, thousand euros	123377 (N1)	107806 (N2)	131763 (N3)
Cost of goods sold, thousand euros	113735 (C1)	121466 (C2)	99382 (C3)

Source: Calculated by the authors.

Table 3. Modelling scenarios

Title of scenario	Compos. of forecasts	Gross profit, thousand euros			Probability, proportion of units	Weighted gross profit, thousand euros		
		PE "Nad"	ALLC "Victory"	LLC "Beevo"		PE "Nad"	ALLC "Victory"	LLC "Beevo"
Optimistic	N3-C2	15.433	9.961	10.297	0.01	154.3	99.6	102.9
Positive 1	N3-C1	19.387	12.751	18.027	0.05	969.4	637.5	901.4
Positive 2	N1-C2	12.767	7.824	1.912	0.07	893.6	547.6	133.8
Positive 3	N3-C3	21.516	14.254	32.380	0.17	3657.6	2423.1	5504.7
Credible	N1-C1	16.721	10.614	9.642	0.40	6688.2	4245.5	3856.9
Negative 1	N2-C2	6.545	3.855	-13.660	0.17	1112.6	655.3	-2322.2
Negative 2	N1-C3	18.849	12.117	23.995	0.07	1319.4	848.1	1679.7
Negative 3	N2-C1	10.499	6.645	-5.929	0.05	525.0	332.3	-296.5
Pessimistic	N2-C3	12.627	8.148	8.424	0.01	126.3	81.5	84.2
Total						15446.6	9870.6	9645.0

Source: Calculated by the authors

consequence, the probability of gross profit of one or another enterprise varies from 9,645 (LLC "Beevo") to 15,447 thousand euros (PE "Nagy") (Figures 3 - 4).

Figure 3. Modelling of scenarios for obtaining forecasts gross revenues amount of agricultural enterprises under conditions of the online market, thousand euros

Figure 4. Probability of the gross profit
Source: Built by the authors

The most probable scenario of gross profit in the amount of 6,688 (PE "Nad") and 4,246 (ALLC "Victory") thousand euros corresponds to the probability 0.4. The optimistic and pessimistic scenarios for these enterprises are unlikely 0.01. As for the gross profit of "Beevo" Ltd., its highest amount will be 5,505 thousand euros with a probability 0.17, which corresponds to the optimistic scenario.

In order to assess the overall effectiveness of strategic logistic management, it is advisable to use an integral coefficient. The integral coefficient of strategic logistic management efficiency depends on the strength of the influence of factors of logistic flows and factors of functional components of the logistic chain and the sensitivity of the internal condition of the agricultural enterprise to the influence of these factors. To analyse the quantitative and qualitative changes in the logistic system of the enterprise with the reflection of the integral effect, we propose to apply the integral indicator of logistic management strategy efficiency, taking into account the synergistic changes in the enterprise:

$$E_{ls} = \frac{P_{qc}}{P_{sis}} \times C_i \quad (2)$$

Where: P_{qc} is an indicator reflecting qualitative shifts through the implementation of the enterprise logistics management strategy; P_{sis} is an indicator reflecting shifts within the logistic system in terms of logistic costs through the implementation of the logistic activity management strategy of the enterprise; C_i is the coefficient of influence of the strategy.

Provided $E_{ls} > 1$, the strategy of the logistic management of the enterprise is appropriate and effective; provided $E_{ls} = 1$ (or close to one), the strategy does not bring significant changes in the logistic system of the enterprise; provided $E_{ls} < 1$, the strategy of logistic management is not appropriate. The proposed approach to the formation of a competitive logistic management strategy will increase the level of competitiveness of agrarian enterprises by developing the logistic management system and the management system as a whole.

One of the main stages in the analysis of logistic risks is their assessment (Figure 5). When identifying the risks of managing the logistic systems of agricultural enterprises, first of all, there is a need to identify all types of risk, specific to these systems, so it is advisable to systematise their assessment in terms of the cause of the possible damage.

Figure 5. Risk assessment system for strategic logistic management of agricultural enterprises in an online marketplace
Source: Built by the authors

Thus, conducting a systematic risks analysis of the strategic management of logistic activity of agricultural enterprises should be a multi-level procedure, which includes a large set of specific knowledge, so the various areas of analysis are carried out by specialized structural units. The problem of the majority of

Ukrainian agricultural enterprises is the lack of a comprehensive study and general conclusion, which leads to making only some adjustments in logistic activity and excludes the possibility of timely decision-making when any problems arise.

4. Conclusions

- Evaluating the implementation of an effective competitive strategy for managing of the logistic activity of agrarian enterprises in the online market will produce positive results, which is reflected in a slowdown in the growth rate of operating costs. The proposed approach meets the requirements for making optimal logistic decisions to ensure the strategic development of the agrarian enterprise, taking into account its nature, i.e. taking into account the logistic role in the enterprise and its strategic orientation.
- The result is an integral indicator of the effectiveness of logistic management strategy, reflecting the integral effect that an agricultural enterprise can get through strategic logistic planning and logistic strategies.
- Forecasting the level of competitiveness of the logistic system of an agricultural enterprise is proposed to carry out with the help of mathematical modelling using artificial neural networks and relevant specialized software (MATLAB, which includes a package of application programs Neural Network Toolbox). On the basis of the usage of artificial neural networks, there were obtained forecast values of indicators of competitiveness of spheres of logistic activity of agrarian enterprises, used in the process of modelling scenarios of development in the formation of a competitive advantage strategy of an agrarian enterprise.
- Given the significant impact of profits and costs of an agricultural enterprise on the formation of indicators of reliability of the logistic system, the scenario approach was applied to determine the value of gross profits, depending on changes in net income and cost of goods sold and conducted scenario simulations (realistic, pessimistic, optimistic).
- To analyse the quantitative and qualitative changes in the logistic system of the enterprise with the reflection of the integral effect, it is proposed to apply the integral indicator of logistic management strategy effectiveness, taking into account the synergistic changes in the enterprise.

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